

**TIP O'ZGARISH CHIZIG'I SILLIQ BO'LMAGAN PARABOLIK-GIPERBOLIK
TENGLAMA UCHUN INTEGRAL ULASH SHARTLI CHEGARAVIY MASALA**

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Abstract: Tip o'zgarish chizig'i silliq bo'lmagan parabolik-giperbolik tenglama uchun integral ulash shartli chegaraviy masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan. Masala yechimining yagonaligi energiya integrallari usulida, mavjudligi esa integral tenglamalar usulida isbotlangan.

Keywords: parabolik-giperbolik tenglama; integral ulash sharti; energiya integrallari; Grin funksiyasi; Dalamber formulasi; integral tenglama

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**BOUNDARY PROBLEM WITH INTEGRAL GLUING CONDITION FOR
PARABOLIC-HYPERBOLIC EQUATION WITH NON-SMOOTH LINE OF
TYPE-CHANGING**

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Abstract: A unique solvability of a boundary problem with integral gluing condition for parabolic-hyperbolic equation with non-smooth line of type-changing has been proved. The uniqueness of the solution to the problem is proved by energy integral's method, the existence by the method of integral equations..

Keywords: Parabolic-hyperbolic equation; integral gluing condition; energy integrals; Green's function; d'Alambert's formula; integral equations

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Bizga Ω sohada quyidagi tenglama berilgan bo'lsin:

$$\begin{cases} U_{xx} - U_y = 0, & (x, y) \in \Omega_0 \\ U_{xx} - U_{yy} = 0, & (x, y) \in \Omega_i, (i = 1, 2) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Ω soha esa quyidagicha $\Omega = \Omega_0 \cup \Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2 \cup AB \cup AA_0$, bu yerda

$$A(0,0); A_0(0,1); B(1,0); B_0(1,1); C\left(\frac{1}{2}, -\frac{1}{2}\right); D\left(-\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}\right) \text{ to'g'ri}$$

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Masala. (1) tenglamani qanoatlantiruvchi Ω sohada shunday $U(x, y)$ funksiya topilsinki, u $U(x, y) \in C_{x,y}^{2,1}(\Omega_0) \cap C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap C^2(\Omega_i), (i=1,2)$ regulyarlik shartlarini hamda quyidagi shartlarni qanoatlantirsin:

$$U(x, y)|_{AC} = \psi_1(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2}, \quad (2)$$

$$U(x, y)|_{AD} = \psi_2(y), \quad -\frac{1}{2} \leq x \leq 0, \quad (3)$$

$$U(x, y)|_{BB_0} = \varphi(y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad (4)$$

$$U_y(x, +0) = I_1(U_y(x, -0)), \quad U_y(x, +0) = U_y(x, -0), \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad (5)$$

$$U_x(+0, y) = I_2(U_x(-0, y)), \quad U_x(+0, y) = U_x(-0, y), \quad 0 < y < 1. \quad (6)$$

Bu yerda I_1 va I_2 lar hozircha ixtiyoriy integral operatorlar.

Ω_0 sohada $U_{xx} - U_y = 0$ tenglama uchun birinchi chegaraviy masala yechimini quyidagicha yozamiz [1]:

$$u(x, y) = \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(\xi) G_1(x, y; \xi, 0) d\xi + \int_0^y \tau_2^+(\eta) G_{1\xi}(x, y; 0, \eta) d\eta - \int_0^y \varphi(\eta) G_{1\xi}(x, t; l, \eta) d\eta$$

bu yerda, $\tau_1^+(x) = U(x, 0), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1,$

$$\tau_2^+(y) = U(0, y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1, \quad \varphi(y) = U(1, y), \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1.$$

Ω_1 sohada $U_{xx} - U_{yy} = 0$ tenglamaning $U(x, -0) = \tau_1^-(x)$, $0 \leq x \leq 1$,
 $U_y(x, -0) = \nu_1^-(x)$, $0 < x < 1$ boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini
Dalamber formulasi orqali yozamiz [2]:

$$U(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} [\tau_1^-(x-y) + \tau_1^-(x+y)] + \frac{1}{2} \int_{x-y}^{x+y} \nu_1^-(z) dz.$$

Bu yechimni (2) shartga bo'ysundiramiz:

$$2\psi_1(x) = \tau_1^-(0) + \tau_1^-(2x) + \int_{2x}^0 \nu_1^-(z) dz, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Endi $2x$ ni x bilan almashtirsak

$$2\psi_1\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) = \tau_1^-(0) + \tau_1^-(x) - \int_0^x \nu_1^-(z) dz, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

hosil bo'ladi. Keyin bu tenglikni x bo'yicha differensiallasak

$$\psi_1'\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) = \tau_1'(x) - \nu_1^-(x), \quad 0 < x < 1 \quad (7)$$

Munosabatni olamiz.

Ω_2 sohada $U_{xx} - U_{yy} = 0$ tenglamaning $U(-0, y) = \tau_2^-(y)$, $0 \leq y \leq 1$,
 $U_x(-0, y) = \nu_2^-(y)$, $0 < y < 1$ boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini
Dalamber formulasi orqali yozamiz [2]:

$$U(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} [\tau_2^-(y-x) + \tau_2^-(y+x)] - \frac{1}{2} \int_{y+x}^{y-x} \nu_2^-(z) dz.$$

Bu yechimni (3) shartga bo'ysundiramiz:

$$2\psi_2(y) = \tau_2^-(2y) + \tau_2^-(0) - \int_0^{2y} \nu_2^-(z) dz, \quad 0 \leq y \leq \frac{1}{2}.$$

Endi $2y$ ni y bilan almashtirsak,

$$2\psi_2\left(\frac{y}{2}\right) = \tau_2^-(y) + \tau_2^-(0) - \int_0^y \nu_2^-(z) dz, \quad 0 \leq y \leq 1$$

hosil bo'ladi. Keyin bu tenglikni y bo'yicha differensiallasak

$$\psi_2'\left(\frac{y}{2}\right) = \tau_2'(y) - \nu_2^-(y), \quad 0 < y < 1 \quad (8)$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Masala yechimining yagonaligi.

Masala yechimi 2 ta u_1 va u_2 funksiyalar bo'lsin. U holda $v = u_1 - u_2$ funksiyaga nisbatan quyidagi masalani qarashimiz mumkin bo'ladi:

$$\begin{cases} v_{xx} - v_y = 0, & (x, y) \in \Omega_0 \\ v_{xx} - v_{yy} = 0, & (x, y) \in \Omega_i, (i=1,2) \end{cases}$$

$$v(x, y)|_{AC} = 0, v(x, y)|_{AD} = 0, \quad v(x, y)|_{BB_0} = 0,$$

$$v_y(x, +0) = I_1(v_y(x, -0)), \quad v_x(+0, y) = I_2(v_x(-0, y))$$

Bu esa bir jinsli tenglama uchun bir jinsli shartli masaladir. Agar ushbu masala yechimining $v(x, y) \equiv 0$ ekanligini ko'rsata olsak, asosiy masalaning yechimi yagonaligi kelib chiqadi:

Dastlab, $v_{xx} - v_y = 0$ tenglamada $y \rightarrow +0$ holda limitga o'tamiz va

$$\tau_1^{+''}(x) - v_1^+(x) = 0$$

tenglamani olamiz. Bu yerda $\tau_1^+(x) = v(x, +0)$, $v_1^+(x) = v_y(x, +0)$ hamda ushbu tenglamani $\tau_1^+(x)$ ga ko'paytirib (0,1) oraliqda integrallaymiz:

$$\int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) \tau_1^{+''}(x) dx - \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) v_1^+(x) dx = 0.$$

Ushbu integralni bo'laklab integrallaymiz:

$$\tau_1^+(x) \tau_1^{+'}(x) \Big|_0^1 - \int_0^1 \left[\tau_1^{+'}(x) \right]^2 dx - \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) v_1^+(x) dx = 0.$$

$\tau_1^+(0) = \tau_1^+(1) = 0$ ekanligini inobatga olsak yuqoridagi ifoda quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\int_0^1 \left[\tau_1^{+'}(x) \right]^2 dx + \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) v_1^+(x) dx = 0$$

Bundan $\int_0^1 \left[\tau_1^{+'}(x) \right]^2 dx \geq 0$ bo'lgani uchun $\int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) v_1^+(x) dx \geq 0$ ekanligini ko'rsata olsak yechim yagonaligini ko'rsatishimiz mumkin bo'ladi. Buning uchun I_1 operatorni quyidagicha tanlaymiz:

$$I_1(f(x)) = \int_0^x f(z) K(x, z) dz.$$

Demak,

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_1 &= \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) \nu_1^+(x) dx = \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) I_1(\tau_1^+(x)) dx = \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) dx \int_0^x \tau_1^+(z) K(x, z) dz = \\
 &= \int_0^1 \tau_1^+(x) dx \left[\tau_1^+(z) K(x, z) \Big|_0^x - \int_0^x \tau_1^+(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial z} K(x, z) dz \right] = \\
 &= \int_0^1 \tau_1^2(x) K(x, x) dx - \int_0^1 \tau_1(x) dx \int_0^x \tau_1^+(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial z} K(x, z) dz.
 \end{aligned}$$

Bundan $K(x, x) \geq 0$ deb olib, $K(x, z)$ uchun quyidagi tenglikni o'rinli deb olsak

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} K(x, z) = -K_1(x) K_1(z),$$

J_1 integralimizni quyidagicha ifodalashimiz mumkin bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^1 \tau_1^2(x) K(x, x) dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{d}{dx} \left[\int_0^x \tau_1^+(z) K_1(z) \right]^2 dz = \\
 &= \int_0^1 \tau_1^2(x) K(x, x) dx + \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_0^1 \tau_1^+(z) K_1(z) dz \right)^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Shunday qilib yuqoridagi shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi $K(x, z)$ funksiya uchun $\tau_1^-(x)$ funksiyani nolga tengligi kelib chiqadi. Bundan esa $\nu_1^-(x)$ funksiyani ham nolga tengligi kelib chiqadi.

Agar $\tau_1^-(x) = 0, \nu_1^-(x) = 0$ bo'lsa D'alamber formulasidan $v(x, y)$ ni $v(x, y) \equiv 0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi, bu esa bizga yechim yagonaligini keltirib chiqaradi.

Endi $v_{xx} - v_y = 0$ tenglamani olib uni v ga ko'paytirib Ω_0 soha bo'yicha integrallaymiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\iint_{\Omega_0} v(v_{xx} - v_y) dx dy = 0 \text{ yoki} \\
 &\iint_{\Omega_0} \left[(v v_x)_x - v_x^2 - \frac{1}{2} (v^2)_y \right] dx dy = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Grin formulasini qo'llab [2], soha bo'yicha integralni soha chegarasi bo'yicha integralga keltiramiz:

$$\int_{\partial\Omega_0} v v_x dy + \frac{1}{2} (v^2) dx - \iint_{\Omega_0} v_x^2 dx dy = 0.$$

Endi chegara bo'yicha integrallashni amalga oshirib olamiz:

$$\int_0^1 \frac{1}{2} [\tau_1^+(x)]^2 dx + \int_0^1 v(1, y) v_x(1, y) dy - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 v^2(x, 1) dx - \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) v_2^+(y) dy - \iint_{\Omega_0} v_x^2(x, y) dx dy = 0.$$

$\tau_1^+(x) = 0, v(1, y) = 0$ ekanligidan integral quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 v^2(x, 1) dx + \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) v_2^+(y) dy + \iint_{\Omega_0} v_x^2(x, y) dx dy = 0.$$

Agar $\int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) v_2^+(y) dy \geq 0$ ni ekanligini ko'rsata olsak yechim yagonaligini

ko'rsatishimiz mumkin.

$$\begin{aligned} J_2 &= \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) v_2^+(y) dy = \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) I_2(\tau_2'(y)) dy = \left\{ I_2(f(x)) = \int_0^x f(x) P(x, z) dz \right\} = \\ &= \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) \left[\int_0^y \tau_2'(z) P(y, z) dz \right] dy = \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) \left[\tau_2^+(z) P(y, z) \Big|_0^y - \int_0^y \tau_2(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial z} P(y, z) dz \right] dy = \\ &= \int_0^1 (\tau_2^+(y))^2 P(y, y) dy - \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) \left[\int_0^y \tau_2(z) \frac{\partial}{\partial z} P(y, z) dz \right] dy = \\ &= \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} P(y, z) = -P_1(y) P_1(z) \right\} = \int_0^1 (\tau_2^+(y))^2 P(y, y) dy + \\ &+ \int_0^1 \tau_2^+(y) \left[\int_0^y \tau_2(z) P_1(y) P_1(z) dz \right] dy = \int_0^1 (\tau_2^+(y))^2 P(y, y) dy + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \frac{d}{dy} \left[\int_0^y \tau_2^+(z) P_1(z) dz \right]^2 dy = \int_0^1 (\tau_2^+(y))^2 P(y, y) dy + \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_0^1 \tau_2^+(z) P_1(z) dz \right]^2 \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Agar $P(y, y) \geq 0$ va $\frac{\partial}{\partial z} P(y, z) = -P_1(y) P_1(z)$ larni ta'minlay olsak $P(y, z)$

funksiya uchun $\tau_2(y)$ funksiyani nolga tengligi kelib chiqadi. Bundan esa $v_2(y)$ funksiyani ham nolga tengligi kelib chiqadi.

Agar $\tau_2(y) = 0, v_2(y) = 0$ bo'lsa D'alamber formulasida $v(x, y)$ ni $v(x, y) \equiv 0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi, bu esa bizga yechim yagonaligini keltirib chiqaradi.

Masala yechimining mavjudligi.

Dastlab (5) va (6) shartlarni quyidagicha ko'rishga keltirib olamiz:

$$v_1^+(x) = I_1(v_1^-(x)), \quad (5)$$

$$v_2^+(x) = I_2(v_2^-(x)). \quad (6)$$

Ω_0 sohada $y \rightarrow +0$ da limitga o'tgan ifodamiz

$$\tau_1^{+''}(x) - v_1^+(x) = 0 \quad (9)$$

va Ω_1 sohada olgan

$$\psi_1'\left(\frac{x}{2}\right) = \tau_1^-(x) - v_1^-(x), \quad 0 < x < 1 \quad (7)$$

munosabatlarimiz hamda $\tau_1^-(0) = \psi_1(0)$, $\tau_1^-(1) = \varphi(0)$ shartlarga asosan quyidagi masalaga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \tau_1^{+''}(x) - I_1(\tau_1^+(x)) = -I_1\left(\psi_1'\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)\right) \\ \tau_1^+(0) = \psi_1(0), \quad \tau_1^+(1) = \varphi(0). \end{cases}$$

$K(x, z)$ yadroni $K(x, z) = K_1(x)K_1(z)$ deb olsak I_1 operatorni

$$I_1(f(x)) = \int_0^x f(z)K_1(x)K_1(z)dz \quad (10)$$

ko'rishga keladi. Natijada quyidagi integral tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$\tau_1^{+''}(x) - \int_0^x \tau_1^+(z)K_1(x)K_1(z)dz = \psi_1(x), \quad (11)$$

bu yerda $\psi_1(x) = -\int_0^x \psi_1'\left(\frac{x}{2}\right)K_1(x)K_1(z)dz$.

Hosil bo'lgan (11) integral tenglamani $(0, x)$ da integrallab

$$\int_0^x \tau_1^{+''}(\xi)d\xi - \int_0^x K_1(\xi)d\xi \int_0^\xi \tau_1^+(z)K_1(z)dz = \int_0^x \psi_1(\xi)d\xi$$

ifodaga ega bo'lamiz va

$$\int_0^x \tau_1''(\xi)d\xi = \tau_1'(x) - \tau_1'(0)$$

ni hisobga olib integrallash tartibini o'zgartirsak quyidagi integral tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$\tau_1^+(x)dx - \int_0^x \tau_1^+(z)K_1(z)dz \int_z^x K_1(\xi)d\xi = \psi_1(x) + \tau_1^+(0)$$

$$\text{bu yerda } \psi_1(x) = \int_0^x \psi_1(\xi) d\xi.$$

Hozircha $\tau_1'(0)$ ni ma'lum deb olib integral tenglamani yechishda davom etamiz va quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritib olamiz:

$$K_1(x, z) = K_1(z) \int_z^x K_1(\xi) d\xi - \text{yadro uzluksiz yoki kichik maxsuslikka ega bo'lishi}$$

mumkin.

$$f(x) = \psi_1(x) + \tau_1'(0) \text{ esa uzluksiz funksiya bo'lsin.}$$

Bularni hisobga olib integral tenglama yechimini rezolventa orqali quyidagicha yozish mumkin bo'ladi:

$$\tau_1'(x) = f(x) + \int_0^x R(x, z) f(z) dz.$$

Bu yerda $R(x, z)$ funksiya $K_1(x, z)$ yadroning rezolventasi.

Ushbu tenglikni $(0, x)$ intervalda integrallab $\tau_1(x)$ funksiyani topamiz.

$$\tau_1(x) - \tau_1(0) = \int_0^x f(\xi) d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) f(z) dz d\xi$$

yoki

$$\tau_1(x) = \int_0^x f(\xi) d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) f(z) dz d\xi + \psi_1(0).$$

Endi yuqorida ma'lum deb olib davom etgan qiymat $\tau_1'(0)$ ni topish uchun quyidagi hisob kitoblarni amalga oshiramiz:

$$\tau_1(x) = \int_0^x [\psi_1(\xi) + \tau_1'(0)] d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) [\psi_1(z) + \tau_1'(0)] dz d\xi + \psi_1(0) \quad (12)$$

yoki

$$\tau_1(x) = \int_0^x \psi_1(\xi) d\xi + \int_0^x \tau_1'(0) d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) \psi_1(z) dz d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) \tau_1'(0) dz d\xi + \psi_1(0).$$

$$\text{Ushbu belgilashni } F(x, z) = \int_0^x \psi_1(\xi) d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) \psi_1(z) dz d\xi + \psi_1(0) \text{ kiritib olib}$$

hisob kitobni sodda ko'rinishda tasvirlashimiz mumkin.

$$\tau_1(x) = \int_0^x \tau_1'(0) d\xi + \int_0^x \int_0^\xi R(x, z) \tau_1'(0) dz d\xi + F(x, z).$$

$x=1$ dagi $\tau_1(x)$ funksiyani qiymatidan foydalangan holda $\tau_1'(0)$ ni topishimiz mumkin bo'ladi:

$$\tau_1(1) = \tau_1'(0) + \tau_1'(0) \int_0^1 \int_0^\xi R(1, z) dz d\xi + \varphi(1, z),$$

$$\tau_1'(0) = \frac{\varphi(0) - \varphi(1, z)}{1 + \int_0^1 \int_0^\xi R(1, z) dz d\xi}.$$

Bundan $\int_0^1 \int_0^\xi R(1, z) dz d\xi \neq -1$ qo'shimcha shartga ega bo'lamiz.

$\tau_1(x)$ - (12) ko'rinishda topilgandan so'ng (7) tenglikdan foydalanib $v_1^+(x)$ ni topish mumkin bo'ladi.

Ulash shartiga ko'ra esa $v_1^-(x)$ aniq ko'rinishda topiladi.

Ω_2 sohada $U_{xx} - U_{yy} = 0$ tenglamaning $U(-0, y) = \tau_2^-(y)$, $0 \leq y \leq 1$, $U_x(-0, y) = v_2^-(y)$, $0 < y < 1$ boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini Dalamber formulasi orqali yozib olamiz [3].

$$U(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} [\tau_2(y-x) + \tau_2(y+x)] - \frac{1}{2} \int_{y+x}^{y-x} v_2^-(z) dz.$$

Bu yechimni (3) shartga bo'ysundirib olgan (8) tengligimizga I_2 operatorni qo'llab

$$I_2 \left(\tau_2'(y) \right) - I_2 \left[\psi_1' \left(\frac{y}{2} \right) \right] = v_2^+(y) \text{ tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.}$$

Keyin esa

$$\begin{aligned} v_2^+(y) = & \int_0^1 \tau_1(\xi) G_{1x}(0, y; \xi, 0) d\xi + \tau_2(\eta) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \Big|_0^y - \\ & - \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta - \varphi(\eta) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \Big|_0^y + \\ & + \int_0^y \varphi'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta \end{aligned}$$

yoki

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2\left(\tau_2'(y)\right) - I_2\left[\psi_1'\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)\right] &= \int_0^1 \tau_1(\xi) G_{1x}(0, y; \xi, 0) d\xi + \tau_2(\eta) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \Big|_0^y - \\
 - \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta - \varphi(\eta) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \Big|_0^y + \\
 + \int_0^y \varphi'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta.
 \end{aligned}$$

Shundan so'ng quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2\left(\tau_2'(y)\right) - I_2\left[\psi_1'\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)\right] &= \int_0^1 \tau_1(\xi) G_{1x}(0, y; \xi, 0) d\xi - \tau_2(0) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y}}} - \\
 - \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta - \varphi(0) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y}}} + \\
 + \int_0^y \varphi'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta.
 \end{aligned}$$

Bu tenglikda ma'lum narsalarni bir tomonga olib o'tsak

$$I_2\left(\tau_2'(y)\right) + \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta = \mathcal{P}_2^0(y) \quad (13)$$

hosil

bo'ladi.

Bu

yerda

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{P}_2^0(y) &= I_2\left[\psi_1'\left(\frac{y}{2}\right)\right] + \int_0^1 \tau_1(\xi) G_{1x}(0, y; \xi, 0) d\xi - \tau_2(0) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y}}} + \\
 + \varphi(0) \cdot \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y}}} + \int_0^y \varphi'(\eta) \left(\sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n+1)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta
 \end{aligned}$$

$$I_2 \text{ operatorni } I_2(g(y)) = \int_0^y g(y) P(y, z) dz \text{ ko'rinishda tanlab olib,} \quad (13)$$

tenglikni quyidagicha yozib olish mumkin:

$$\int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta = \mathcal{P}_2^0(y). \quad (14)$$

(14) tenglikni y bo'yicha differensiallab quyidagi integral tenglamaga kelamiz:

$$\tau_2'(\eta) \left\{ \lim_{\eta \rightarrow y} \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) \right\} +$$

$$+ \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) d\eta = \mathcal{P}_2'(y).$$

$$\lim_{\eta \rightarrow y} \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) = \mathcal{P}_2'(y) \text{ belgilash kiritib, } \mathcal{P}_2'(y) \neq 0 \text{ deb olib}$$

tenglamani har ikki tomoniga bo'lib yuborsak

$$\tau_2'(\eta) + \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) \frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right)}{\mathcal{P}_2'(y)} d\eta = \frac{\mathcal{P}_2'(y)}{\mathcal{P}_2'(y)}$$

hosil bo'ladi.

$$\frac{\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right)}{\mathcal{P}_2'(y)} = Q(y, \eta); \quad \frac{\mathcal{P}_2'(y)}{\mathcal{P}_2'(y)} = \Phi(y);$$

belgilashlarni kiritib olamiz.

$Q(y, \eta)$ - yadro uzluksiz yoki 1 dan kichik maxsuslikka ega, $\Phi(y)$ -funksiya esa uzluksiz bo'lsa, $\tau_2'(\eta) + \int_0^y \tau_2'(\eta) Q(y, \eta) d\eta = \Phi(y)$ Volterra 2-tur integral tenglama quyidagi yechimga ega:

$$\tau_2'(\eta) = \Phi(y) + \int_0^y \Phi(y) R_2(y, \eta) d\eta.$$

$R_2(y, \eta)$ - $Q(y, \eta)$ yadroning rezolventasi.

$\tau_2'(y)$ ni (8) tenglikka olib borib qo'yib $v_2^-(x)$ ni topish mumkin bo'ladi.

Topilganlarga asosan qo'yilgan $\{(1),(2),(3),(4),(5)\}$ masala yechimini Ω_0 sohada 1-chegaraviy masala yechimi ko'rinishda Ω_1 va Ω_2 da esa Dalamber formulasi orqali tiklab ko'rsatish mumkin.

Shunday qilib quyidagi tasdiq o'rinli ekanligini isbotladik:

Teorema. Agar

$$K(x, z) = K_1(x)K_1(z), \frac{\partial}{\partial z} K(x, z) = -K_1(x)K_1(z), K(x, x) \geq 0, \int_0^1 \int_0^\xi R(1, z) dz d\xi \neq -1$$

$$, \frac{\partial}{\partial z} P(y, z) = -P_1(y)P_1(z), P(y, y) \geq 0,$$

$$\lim_{\eta \rightarrow y} \left(P(y, \eta) + \sum_{n=-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{1}{\sqrt{y-\eta}} e^{-\frac{(2n)}{\sqrt{y-\eta}}} \right) = P(y) \neq 0, \varphi(y), \psi_i(x) \in C^1[0, 1], (i=1, 2),$$

$$I_1(f(x)) = \int_0^x f(z)K(x, z)dz, I_2(g(y)) = \int_0^y g(y)P(y, z)dz$$

shartlar bajarilsa, u holda masalaning yechimi mavjud va yagona.

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